

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D 2.6.2 “New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in Collaboration with Companies)”

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M8 to M 36
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Deliverable # Responsible	Arlorio
RM2 Responsible	Arlorio

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List of RM2 Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	Delivery Date (actual)
<i>[number]</i>	<i>[name]</i>	<i>[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]</i>	<i>[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]</i>	<i>[month number]</i>	<i>[dd/mm/yyyy]</i>
D2.1	Data about chemical and nutritional profiling of raw wastes and by products	R	PU	M14	18/04/2024
D2.2.1	On-line lab-scale technical multi-device for waste processing*	Other (material)	PU	M18	25/10/2024
D2.2.2	Delivery of protocols (lab-scale) ready to scale-up the production of new high-value material (in collaboration with Companies)	R	PU	M22	16/02/2025
D2.3.1	New data about valorized matrices characterization and high value products	R	PU	M28	30/09/2025
D2.3.2	New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharma and cosmetic applications	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.4.1	New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomasses	R	PU	M24	24/12/2025
D2.4.2	New characterized materials from biomasses	Other (material) (& Report)	PU	M30	29/09/2025
D2.5.2	Porous sorbents from biomasses valorization	Other (material) (& Report)	PU	M30	29/09/2025
D2.6.1	New material produced at pilot scale ready to the formulation or co-formulation (in collaboration with Companies)	Other (material) (& Report)	PU	M32	30/09/2025
D2.6.2	New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in collaboration with Companies)	R/Other (Material)	PU	M32	24/12/2025

D2.7	Report on the adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	R	PU	M32	29/09/2025
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A) INTRODUCTION

The main outcome reported in this Deliverable is related to the description of the design and the production of three pilot scale model products (food supplements; cosmetics) formulated using selected valorised (and characterized ingredients) as described in D.2.3.1, D.2.3.2, D. 2.4.2 and listed in D 6.2.2.

After the complete characterization of the best performing (single or combined) bio-based and green technological processes, the work allowed to obtain some well characterized ingredient, ready to be scaled up as well as to be used in model products.

B) ROLE OF PARTNERS

As described in the preliminary Deliverables as well as detailed in the Project (RM2, GRIP PROJECT), all the Partners worked in synergy (and also complementarily) in order i) to estimate the value of each single bio-based/green process, ii) to evaluate the best performing approaches useful to valorise/upcycle raw organic materials (liquid and solid; biomasses from environmental origin; waste and by-products from agrifood chains).

The main outcome of the overall work were:

- *new processed valorised raw material*
- *new ingredients/fractions from processed raw materials, ready to be used in different areas (chemical, nutraceutical, cosmetical, pharmaceutical)*
- *new "model products" as proof of concepts for the entire RM2 research activities, formulated and developed in collaboration with some Companies.*

Moreover, each Partner developed specific solution that – beside the three final model products here described – will be probably able in the future enabling new applied researches or new processes, allowing to obtain more products and more applications in a real industrial environment (e.g. the valorization of recalcitrant biomasses useful to be added as "additives" in cement or in plastic materials, or porous material for environmental applications, as described in D2.5.2 and D2.7).

Unit DSF-UPO, depending on i) the broad availability of valorised materials (essentially derived from the cocoa bean husks, apple pomace and fruit pomace up-cycling),

produced in small pilot scale, and ii) depending on the large collaboration with pharmaceutical, nutraceutical and cosmetic Companies, proceeded with the production of two food supplements and a cosmetic formula (emulgel), as following described.

The Companies involved in this part of the Project were Procemsa Company (Turin; the Company funded a PhD program); ProgeFarm Company (Novara) and APTsol Company (Novara). The collaboration with the companies was strategic especially in the phases of the product formulation and pilot production.

C) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The three proof of concepts (POCs) here considered the final model products as result of the overall research, were prepared using:

- *Prebiotic fiber/antioxidant polyphenols from cocoa bean husks*
- *Fiber from apple pomace*
- *Phloretin/phlorizin/polyphenol rich ingredients from apple pomace*
- *Polyphenols rich extract from blueberry pomace*

Model product 1 – Capsules (food supplement) – developed in collaboration with Farmaceutici Procemsa Company

Rationale: the main idea related to the development of a new food supplement, was focused on the valorization of cocoa fibers from cocoa bean shells processed as described in Deliverables (more particularly selecting the process developed by ultrasounds and enzyme-driven hydrolysis of carbohydrates, in order to obtain a prebiotic-like oligosaccharides-rich up-cycled dietary fiber. The bioactivity of this ingredient was established in collaboration with other NODES project (particularly GREENVAL UPO POC project and some Industrial POCs), confirming the usefulness in boosting the production in vitro of Short Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs). These overall activities can be considered a success correlated with the intra-fertilization system of research of Nodes. This ingredient was formulated together with the ingredient obtained from the valorized apple pomace extract, enriched in phloridzin and polyphenols. The rationale was to develop a food supplements useful to control the glycemic index (apple ingredient) also regulating the microbiota (cocoa ingredient rich in prebiotic fibers).

In synthesis, in collaboration with *Farmaceutici Procemsa S.p.A.*, capsules of 0.5 mL were produced containing 0.3 g of cocoa bean shells-derived ingredients (obtained with ultrasound and enzymatic hydrolysis, as described in previous deliverables). This specific treatment resulted in the highest content of oligosaccharides, fermentable sugars, and antioxidant activity among the tested preparations. The formulation also included 3% (w/w) of dried apple pomace extract, a source particularly rich in phloridzin, which was incorporated to enhance the nutraceutical profile of the product. The capsules were successfully produced using standard encapsulation processes and demonstrated good technological and chemical stability upon preliminary evaluation (Figure 2). Moreover, a pilot production were obtained in collaboration with the Company, active also in the formulation step.

Initial tests also indicated that the capsules possessed satisfactory gastric resistance, suggesting that the release of bioactive compounds may primarily occur in the intestinal environment—an aspect favorable for the delivery of prebiotic oligosaccharides and antioxidant polyphenols. The combination of cocoa shell and apple pomace extracts therefore represents a promising formulation for supporting gut health and counteracting oxidative stress, as well as potentially modulating glycaemia. The achieved results will permit more investigation (in vitro and in vivo trials are planned with future projects).

Figure 1. Spray-drying system

Figure 2. Tablets obtained using a capsule-filling machine based on cocoa and apple pomace extract.

Model product 2 – Tablets (food supplement) – Developed in collaboration with Proge Farm Srl and APTSol Srl Companies

Rationale: the main idea was to valorize the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory property of the polyphenol-rich extract prepared from cocoa bean shells, as described in the previous Deliverables. The tablets (beside the large use of the capsules) are still considered a pharmaceutical form useful to deliver bioactive compounds, as well as largely used both in pharma and food areas.

More precisely, in collaboration with Progefarm Srl, tablets were first formulated and then produced using a base mixture composed of lactose, crospovidone, and povidone, to which micronized cocoa bean shells-derived ingredients were added at two different inclusion levels (5 and 10% w/w) (Figure 4). The mixture ensured suitable flowability and compressibility, allowing for efficient tableting without the need for additional excipients. The formulations containing 10% cocoa shell powder were successfully compressed, yielding tablets with uniform weight and appearance, appropriate hardness, and good disintegration properties. However, preliminary scaling-up simulations indicated the need to further evaluate the behavior of the ingredients under larger industrial production conditions. Indeed, when increasing the cocoa shell content to 15%, difficulties arose during compression due to poor powder flow and the irregular shape of the resulting tablets. These findings suggest that 10% represents a practical upper limit for cocoa shell incorporation under the current formulation and processing conditions, and further optimization will be required to improve processability at higher inclusion levels.

The produced tablets showed good physical stability over time and retained a significant antioxidant capacity/anti-inflammatory capacity attributable to the polyphenolic fraction of cocoa shells. These properties make the tablets suitable candidates for further nutraceutical developments, particularly in formulations targeting oxidative stress reduction and general metabolic well-being, also permitting to add more additional ingredients (e.g. specific vitamins).

Figure 3. Bench-top pilot table-press

Figure 4. Control tablets (A), and tablets with 5% (B) and 10% (C) cocoa content, respectively from top to bottom.

Model product 3 – Emulgel (cosmetic) – Developed in collaboration with APTsol srl Company

Rationale: the emulgel formula is relatively-new largely used form in pharma-related and cosmetic applications, so an interesting target for the RM2 project. The main idea in this case was to develop a multi-applications final “model product” potentially useful in cosmetic, food and pharmaceutical areas. The use of NaDES-driven extraction allowed to obtain an organic solvent-free process starting from blueberry pomace. This final product was completely characterized, opening new perspectives in cosmetic/pharmaceutical but also in food areas.

More particularly, as well know, an “emulgel” (Fig. 5) in cosmetic area is a type of topical formulation that combines an emulsion with a gelling agent, creating a gel-like structure that is highly effective for delivering both hydrophobic (water-repelling) and hydrophilic (water-attracting) active ingredients, such as medications or nutrients, to the skin. This dual-component system offers advantages like improved stability, controlled release of the active substances, good spreadability, a non-greasy feel, and cosmetic appeal, making it a popular choice in dermatology and cosmetics. Moreover, beside the typical properties of the emulgel, it is a promising carrier systems for food ingredients and drugs. Novel delivery systems for cosmetics, drugs (and also food ingredients) are of great scientific and industrial interest due to their ability to incorporate and protect active substances, thus improving their selectivity, bioavailability, and efficacy.

Figure 5. Schematic scheme and flowchart of an emulgel formation (Source: Milutinov, J.; Krstonošić, V.; Ćirin, D.; Pavlović, N. *Emulgels: Promising Carrier Systems for Food Ingredients and Drugs. Polymers* 2023, 15, 2302. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15102302>)

These were the reasons why the formulation of an emulgel using some ingredients obtained from food by- and co-products was selected as model for the development of an innovative product as outcome of the RM2.

More particularly, the aim of this application (formulated in collaboration with APTsol, Novara) was to develop topical system in the form of an emulgel containing a polyphenolic extract obtained from blueberry waste using a natural eutectic solvent (NaDES).

First, the extract demonstrated marked biological activity: it inhibited elastase more effectively than the ethanol counterpart and showed comparable tyrosinase inhibition across tested dilutions, as previously reported in D2.3.1 + D2.3.2.

These activities are particularly relevant for anti-aging applications, as both enzymes are involved in skin degradation and pigmentation.

Figure 6. Anti-elastase activity (%) of NaDES-extract and Et50-extract.

Building on these results, the Bet:CA extract was incorporated at 10% into an oil-in-water emulgel (Em1), using another ingredient developed during RM2 research activity: *apricot kernel oil*, as the lipid phase. The formulation was stable, homogeneous, and exhibited a lilac coloration, in contrast to the white control emulgels. Rheological analysis revealed a pseudoplastic and thixotropic behavior, with viscosity values around 10,000 mPa·s for Em1 and Em2, significantly higher than the 6,000 mPa·s of the control (Em3). This increase is attributed to electrostatic interactions promoted by citric acid and betaine, which enhanced the polymeric network structure.

Crucially, the bioactive properties of the extract were preserved within the emulgel. Antioxidant assays performed on the formulations confirmed that Em1 retained strong activity across DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP tests, while both blank and control emulgels showed negligible bioactivity.

Figure 7. Antioxidant activity of emulgels. Em1 10% extract ; Em2: ; Em3: control (no extract).

This indicates that the NaDES extract not only survived incorporation but remained functionally active in the final cosmetic product.

Figura 8. Sample of the final product (emulgel prepared with NaDES extract from blueberry pomace)

Overall, the study demonstrates that blueberry pomace can be efficiently valorized using green NaDES extraction, yielding phenolic-rich extracts with antioxidant, anti-elastase, and anti-tyrosinase properties. Their successful formulation into an emulgel with apricot kernel oil highlights both technological feasibility and market potential, paving the way for innovative and sustainable cosmetic applications.